

A simple spectrophotometric method for determination of antimony(III) with *N*-bromosuccinimide and methyl orange

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Abstract : In this study, a simple and sensitive spectrophotometric method for the determination of antimony(III) is described. It is based on the oxidation of antimony(III) with slight excess of *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS) in acidic medium and the unconsumed (NBS) is determined with methyl orange (λ_{max} 500 nm). Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range of 0.4–2.8 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for antimony(III). The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $3.43 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0035 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of Sb^{III} in water, soil and biological samples.

Keywords : Spectrophotometric determination, antimony(III), NBS, methyl orange.

Introduction

Antimony is found in nature mainly in the form of stibnite (Sb_2S_3). It is estimated that the amount of antimony in the earth's crust range from 0.2 to 0.5 ppm. Small amount of oxide mineral also known as valentinite (Sb_2O_3), cerventile (Sb_2O_4) and stibiconite ($\text{Sb}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) are also commonly found along with copper, silver and lead ores. Antimony and its compounds are industrially important because of their usefulness in the manufacture of alloys, paper, plastics, textile, glass, clay products and rubber. It is also used in lead storage batteries, solder, sheet and pipe metal, bearings, castings and pewter. Exposure to antimony at high levels can irritate eyes and cause lung diseases, heart problems, diarrhea, severe vomiting and stomach ulcers. EPA allows 0.006 part per million of antimony in drinking water. The threshold limit for exposure of antimony and its compounds in air are $0.5 \text{ mg M}^{-3} \text{ }^{1-5}$. The toxicity of antimony depends on its oxidation state i.e. elemental antimony is more toxic than its salts, while antimony(III) compounds are reported to be more toxic than antimony(V) compounds⁶⁻⁸. The International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) has assigned antimony trioxide to the group of substance that are suspected to be carcinogens⁹. Therefore its

determination is of significant importance from the environmental and health point of view.

Several methods have been reported for the determination of antimony which includes FAAS¹⁰, HG-ICP-AES¹¹, HG-AAS¹², HPLC-ICP-MS¹³, differential pulse anodic stripping voltammetry¹⁴, flow analysis hydride generation, Fourier transform infrared spectrometry¹⁵, potentiometry¹⁶, forced-flow liquid chromatography¹⁷ etc. However, all these techniques are costly, time consuming and require high maintenance. Several reagents have been reported for the determination of antimony at trace levels spectrophotometrically¹⁸⁻²⁶. Some of these reagents are sensitive but have poor selectivity. The purpose of the present study is to develop a low cost, simple analytical method for the determination of antimony.

In this method antimony(III) is oxidized with slight excess of NBS to form an oxidation product. The unconsumed NBS reacts with methyl orange in acidic medium leading to a decrease in the intensity of the dye, which is measured at 500 nm with a spectrophotometer. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of antimony(III) in soil, water and biological samples.

Scheme 1. Reaction of antimony(III).

Results and discussion

Spectral characteristics : The maximum absorbance of methyl orange was found to be at 500 nm against distilled water. Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range 0.4 to 2.8 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for antimony(III). The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $3.43 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0035 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The reproducibility of the method was checked by analyzing 40 μg of antimony(III) per 25 ml for a period of seven days. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.01186 and 2.83% respectively.

Colour reaction : Methyl orange gives maximum absorbance at 500 nm. The following reaction occurs (Scheme 1) : Oxidation of Sb^{III} by NBS in acidic medium and the unreacted NBS then bleaches the colour of methyl orange dye and the absorbance is measured at 500 nm.

Optimization of reaction conditions : In the first stage for oxidation of antimony(III), 0.6–0.7 ml of NBS was necessary and 1.2 ml of methyl orange was required for completion of the experimental process. It was found that acidic medium was necessary for better results. Since nitric acid and sulphuric acid are oxidizing in nature,

hydrochloric acid is used. Best results were obtained with 1 ml 2 M HCl for oxidation of antimony(III). After addition of methyl orange only 2 min was required for its bleaching. The suitable temperature range for the reaction was found to be between 25–30 °C, above and below which absorbance was affected. To assess the validity of the proposed method, effect of various common ions on the determination of antimony(III) were studied. Tolerance limits for various copollutants associated with 40 $\mu\text{g}/25 \text{ ml}$ antimony are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Effect of foreign species on the determination (40 $\mu\text{g}/25 \text{ ml}$) of antimony

Foreign species	Tolerance limit ^a ($\mu\text{g/ml}^{-1}$)
PO_4^{3-}	2100
CO_3^{2-}	2000
SO_4^{2-}	2000
Mg^{2+}	2000
Se^{4+}	1000
Ca^{2+}	1000
As^{3+}	500
V^{3+}	150
Ti^{+}	50
Fe^{2+}	10

^aTolerance limit may vary the absorbance values by $\pm 2\%$.

Note

Table 2. Comparison with other spectrophotometric methods

Sl. no.	Reagents	pH/acidity	Solvent	λ_{\max} (nm)	Molar absorptivity ($L \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	Remark
1.	Rhodamine-6G ¹⁹	Acidic medium	Benzene	535	1.065×10^4	Extraction with benzene
2.	Brilliant green ²¹ and amidine	Hydrochloric acid medium	Toluene	645	1.90×10^5	Extraction with toluene
3.	Bromopyrogallol red ²³	Acidic medium	Water	560	3.672×10^4	Poor sensitivity and selectivity
4.	Iodide ion <i>N</i> -phenyl benzimidoyl thiourea + cetyl pyridinium chloride ²⁰	Acidic medium	Chloroform	440	7.84×10^4	Extraction with chloroform
5.	KI + dithiozone ²⁴	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	Acetone	507	2.56×10^4	Less sensitivity metal ion i.e. Fe ³⁺ , Cu ²⁺ interfere
6.	Cetyl pyridinium chloride + TX 100 + brilliant green ²⁵	2.0–6.0 M HCl	Toluene	620	5.55×10^4	Sensitivity but less selectivity
7.	NBS + methyl orange in acidic medium Present method	2 M HCl	Water	500	3.43×10^4	Simple and sensitive, free from interferences common ions and toxicants

Experimental

A Toshniwal TVSP (Model 25) spectrophotometer and a Systronics digital pH meter (Model 331) were used for spectral and pH measurements. All reagents used were of analytical grade and double distilled water was used throughout the experiment.

Stock solution of standard Sb^{III} solution (Loba chemie, India) (1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was prepared by dissolving 0.2668 g potassium antimony tartarate in 100 ml of water. A working standard solution was prepared by suitable dilution of the standard solution as and when required. 0.02 g of methyl orange was dissolved in 20 ml ethyl alcohol and volume made up to 100 ml with distilled water. 2 M aqueous solution of hydrochloric acid was prepared. 0.02 g of NBS was dissolved in 100 ml distilled water. The solution was prepared daily.

Procedure :

An aliquot of the sample solution containing 10–70 μg of antimony(III) were transferred into a series of 25 ml calibrated flask to which 1 ml 2 M hydrochloric acid and

0.6 ml of NBS were added successively and the solution was kept with occasional shaking for about 10 min at 30 °C and then 1.2 ml of methyl orange solution was added and mixed thoroughly. The volume was made up to 25 ml mark and after 2 min, the absorbance was measured at 500 nm against a reagent blank. A blank without antimony(III) (dye and NBS) was prepared in a similar manner and its absorbance was measured against distilled water. The decrease in absorbance corresponding to consumed oxidant which reflects the antimony concentration was obtained by subtracting the decrease in absorbance of the test solution (dye minus test) from that of the blank solution (dye minus blank). Calibration graph was prepared by plotting the decrease in absorbance of the dye against the amount of the antimony(III).

Application :

In biological samples : To assess the applicability of the method to biological samples, known amount of antimony(III) was added to urine and deproteinised blood samples²⁷. They were then analyzed by present and reported method²⁶. Iron is masked with 1 ml (1%) EDTA. The recovery was found to be 96–98%.

In soil : A known amount (2 g) of soil sample spiked with known amount of antimony(III) was taken to which 6 M HCl was added and the solution was filtered and the filtrate was extracted with 10 ml chloroform. The extract was evaporated and then diluted with water. Iron is masked with 1 ml (1%) EDTA and analyzed by the present and reported method. The recovery was found to be 96–98%.

Determination of antimony in waste water :

Waste water samples were filtered with Whatman filter No. 42 and spiked with known amount of antimony(III). To this 6 M HCl was added and extracted with chloroform. The extract was dried and diluted with water and analyzed by the present and reported method. The recovery was found to be 96–98%.

Conclusion :

The method is very simple, rapid, sensitive, non extractive and reproducible. As the method is based on bleaching action of dyes, the proposed method has been compared with other spectrophotometric methods (Table 2) and was successfully applied to the determination of antimony in water, soil and biological samples.

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References

1. New scientist, "Earth's Natural Wealth; An Audit", 2007.
2. B. M. Sager, M. M. Rajmane and M. A. Anuse, *J. Surb. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **69**, 283.
3. N. N. Greenwood and A. Earnshaw, "Chemistry of the Elements", 2nd ed., Butterworth-Heinemann, An Imprint of Elsevier, 2005, pp. 548-550.
4. Agency for Toxic Substances and Diseases Registry (ATSDR) 1992, Toxicological profile for antimony. Atlanta, G.A. US Department of Health and Public Health Services.

5. F. A. Patty, "Industrial Hygiene and Toxicology", 2nd ed., New York, 1961, Vol. II.
6. T. D. Luckey and Venugopal, "Metal Toxicity in Mammals: Physiologic and Chemical Base for Metal Toxicity". Plenum Press, New York, 1997.
7. H. B. Hou and H. Narasaki, *Anal. Sci.*, 1999, **5**, 911.
8. R. Iffland, "Antimony in handbooks on Toxicity of Inorganic Compounds", Marcel Dekker, New York, 1988, p. 67.
9. World Health Organization International Agency for the Research on Cancer, "IARC Monographs on the Evolution of Carcinogenic Risks to Humans, Antimony Trioxide and Antimony Trisulfide", 1989, **47**, 291.
10. Zhefeng Fan, *Microchimica Acta*, 2005, **152**, 29.
11. Y. L. Feng, N. Narasaki, H. Y. Chen and L. C. Tian, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1999, **386**, 297.
12. S. Hirata, K. Okudo, M. Shibata and M. Aihara, *Bunseki Kagaku*, 1997, **46**, 831.
13. T. Guerin, M. Astruc, A. Batel and M. Borsier, *Talanta*, 1997, **44**, 220.
14. P. A. Waller and W. F. Pickering, *Talanta*, 1995, **42**, 197.
15. M. Gallignani, C. Ayala, M. R. Brunetto, M. Burguera and J. L. Burguera, *Talanta*, 2002, **59**, 923.
16. M. Ponikvar, B. Pihlar and B. Zemva, *Talanta*, 2002, **58**, 803.
17. Larry R. Taylor and Dennis Johnson, *Analytical Chemistry*, 1974, **46**, 262.
18. S. D. Harvey and J. D. Alexander, *Journal of Pharmaceutical Science*, 2006, **56**, 1641.
19. S. Nalini, T. V. Ramakrishna and N. Balasubramanian, *Fresenius J. Anal. Chem.*, 1994, **348**, 769.
20. K. Agarwal, N. Harmukh and K. Shrivastava, *J. of Hazardous Materials*, 2008, **155**, 173.
21. A. Kamavisdar, *Chemia Analytyczna*, 2000, **45**, 893.
22. T. Matsuo, Y. Kuroyanagi and S. Meguro, *Bunseki Kagaku*, 1963, **12**, 515.
23. W. F. Jardim, J. G. Dorea and S. Rath, *Fresenius J. Anal. Chem.*, 1997, **358**, 548.
24. A. Raychoudhary and S. K. Roy, *Talanta*, 1994, **41**, 171.
25. A. N. Tripathi and K. S. Patel, *Fresenius J. Anal. Chem.*, 1998, **360**, 270.
26. K. K. Tiwari, G. L. Mundhara and V. K. Gupta, *Analytical Sciences*, 2006, **22**, 259.
27. M. K. Rai, K. N. Ramchandran and V. K. Gupta, *Analyst*, 1994, **119**, 1883.